

EGU25-16240: EVIDENCE OF GAMMA-RAY GLOWS OBSERVED IN THE RELATIVISTIC FEEDBACK REGIME DURING THE ALOFT 2023 FLIGHT CAMPAIGN

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ABSTRACT

In July 2023, the ALOFT flight campaign deployed an ER-2 research aircraft that flew at 20 km altitude above thunderstorms, carrying an extensive suite of instruments. The campaign observed numerous gamma-ray glows exhibiting complex and highly dynamic morphologies (Marisaldi et al. 2024). This study focuses on two specific glow events recorded on July 29th 2023, between 20:30:20 and 20:31:40 UTC over Florida. By combining Monte Carlo simulations with observations from hard-radiation instruments and ground-based interferometers, we can estimate the multiplication factor required, based on cosmic-ray secondary electrons, to produce gamma-ray glows of the observed magnitude (exceeding 8 times the background level on the ALOFT-BGO detector).

Our analysis reveals multiplication factors of seed electrons (cosmic-ray secondaries) significantly exceeding 5000, occurring multiple times and persisting for periods of several seconds. According to previous studies (Dwyer et al. 2007; Kelley et al. 2015), such high multiplication factors indicate substantial contribution from the Relativistic Feedback Discharge mechanism. Using the methodology established by Kelley et al. (2015), we estimated that the discharge currents resulting from the relativistic process during high-intensity phases of the glow could range in the tens to hundreds of amperes. These values substantially exceed those previously reported by Kelley et al. (2015) and could be large enough to significantly influence the thunderstorm's charging rate.

This study provides evidence that the Relativistic Runaway Electron Avalanche process, amplified by the relativistic feedback mechanism, could compete with conventional discharge mechanisms in certain thunderstorm conditions.

OBJECTIVES

- Quantify the Relativistic Runaway Electron Multiplication factors (from cosmic-ray seed electrons) during ALOFT gamma-ray-glow events.
- Determine whether these events operate within the Relativistic Feedback Discharge (RFD) regime [Dwyer, 2007, 2012].
- Evaluate whether RFD processes plausibly account for the observed reduction or termination of the gamma-ray glows (self-quenching through positive ions left-over of RREA+feedback), and not traditional mechanisms.

PRE-REQUIRED QUANTITIES (COSMIC ELECTRONIC FLUXES, TRANSMISSION COEFFICIENT AND DETECTION EFFICIENCY)

Stage 1 – Cosmic-ray Seed-electron fluxes

- Use the PARMA model [Sato et al., 2008] to compute cosmic-ray secondary (background) electron spectra below 20 km.
- Use 300 keV lower-energy threshold and assume negligible geographic with ER-2 motion within few minutes.
- Resulting flux peaks at $\sim 1.23 \text{ e}^- \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 18 km, falling to ~ 0.88 at 12 km (see Fig. A.).

Stage 2 – Photon transmission from RREA

- Launch upward RREA electrons (11–17 km grid source altitude) into a GEANT4 Monte-Carlo transport to record bremsstrahlung photons reaching 20 km.
- Employ a classical Electron RREA spectrum: power-law $S \propto \epsilon^k$ between 300–800 keV ($k = -0.258$) and an exponential tail above 800 keV ($\epsilon_c = 7.3 \text{ MeV}$).
- Evaluate altitude-dependent transmission coefficients, e.g.: 7.4×10^{-4} (11 km), 1.4×10^{-3} (15 km) due to atmospheric attenuation.

Stage 3 – ALOFT-BGO detector response

- Build a detailed GEANT4 mass model of the BGO detector and instrument housing to generate an energy-response matrices (angle dependent).
- Convolve transmitted photon spectra with the 0-angle matrix to derive the effective area and detection efficiency above the 300 keV threshold.
- Efficiency is ~ 0.63 and changes only slightly with source altitude.

MODELING AND ANALYSIS STRATEGY

Seed-electron multiplication at the source

$$M(t) = \frac{f(t) - B}{T_h S_{h-\delta h} A E_h} \quad (4)$$

- $f(t)$ – observed at 20 km altitude X/γ -ray flux (counts s^{-1})
- B – BGO background at 20 km (≈ 2290 counts s^{-1})
- T_h – transmission from source altitude h to 20 km
- $S_{h-\delta h}$ – cosmic-ray secondary-electron flux at start of acceleration region; fix $\delta h = 1 \text{ km}$
- A – detector area (cm^2)
- E_h – detector efficiency (≈ 0.63 , weakly altitude-dependent)

RREA-driven discharge current density

$$J = 2e \alpha \lambda_{cl} F^{re}, \quad F^{re} = S_{h-\delta h} M \quad (5)$$

- Due to left-over positive ions drifting (typical motion time of 0.5 to 1 second)
- F^{re} – relativistic-electron flux (m^{-2})
- $\alpha = 8350 N_h \text{ m}^{-1}$ – ion pairs per runaway-electron path
- $\lambda_{cl} = 20 \text{ m}$ – ion mean free path (fixed)

Decomposition of M when feedback factor $\gamma < 1$

$$M = e^\xi \frac{1}{1-\gamma} \quad (6)$$

e^ξ is RREA multiplication (ξ is number of avalanche lengths); $(1-\gamma)^{-1} > 1$ is the boost from relativistic feedback

MONTE-CARLO MODELING MAIN RESULTS

Time point h	Current Densities				
	11 km	12 km	13 km	14 km	15 km
T1 (≈ 5000 cts/s)					
change in slope	$4.36 \mu\text{A}/\text{m}^2$	$1.78 \mu\text{A}/\text{m}^2$	$0.75 \mu\text{A}/\text{m}^2$	$0.32 \mu\text{A}/\text{m}^2$	$0.14 \mu\text{A}/\text{m}^2$
in first glow					
T2 (≈ 10000 cts/s)					
top of first glow	$12.42 \mu\text{A}/\text{m}^2$	$5.05 \mu\text{A}/\text{m}^2$	$2.12 \mu\text{A}/\text{m}^2$	$0.91 \mu\text{A}/\text{m}^2$	$0.41 \mu\text{A}/\text{m}^2$
T3 (≈ 19000 cts/s)					
top of	$26.92 \mu\text{A}/\text{m}^2$	$10.97 \mu\text{A}/\text{m}^2$	$4.61 \mu\text{A}/\text{m}^2$	$1.99 \mu\text{A}/\text{m}^2$	$0.89 \mu\text{A}/\text{m}^2$
second glow / glow burst					
(using 1 second time bin)					

- Shows the multiplication factor required at the avalanche-end altitude h to reproduce various BGO-detector count rates.
- Five curves correspond to total (signal + background) rates of 3 000, 5 000, 10 000, 15 000, and 20 000 counts s^{-1} , where the background alone is ≈ 2290 counts s^{-1} .
- The avalanche ends at altitude h ; the acceleration region typically extends 1–2 km below that point, with a characteristic avalanche length of $\approx 150 \text{ m}$. Most electrons are produced within the last two avalanche lengths.
- Boundaries:
 - Gray band: multiplication > 5000 at source is \Rightarrow when relativistic feedback dominates the runaway-electron growth [Kelley et al., 2015].**
 - Red band and dashed line: altitude range and most-probable h inferred from CFLMA charge-distribution data.
- Example: when the observed rate exceeds 5 000 cps and the avalanche end is $\leq 13 \text{ km}$ altitude we are certainly in the relativistic-feedback regime.
- These multiplication factors (via Eq. 3) allow direct marking of feedback-dominated intervals on the measured light-curve.
- During the examined glows, BGO count peaks ranged from ≈ 3000 cps (minor glow) up to ≈ 19000 cps (main glow).

- Times T1, T2 and T3 are indicated in figure D.
- Current density J evaluated at T1 (20:30:27), T2 (20:30:31) and T3 (20:30:55 UTC) for several end-of-avalanche heights h .
- At $h = 13 \text{ km}$, J is 4–26 times larger than the earlier record of $0.18 \mu\text{A}/\text{m}^2$ [Kelley et al., 2015].
- Assuming an acceleration-region horizontal radius of 4 km, the total current is $I = 12 \text{ A}$ (T1), 53 A (T2) and 74 A (T3). Which is very high. Radius is very uncertain and can be reduced.
- Such high “RREA discharge currents” can markedly alter thunderstorm charge. (Relativistic feedback only boosts RREA, it is not the current itself)

REAL GAMMA-RAY GLOWS AND RESULTS

Two Gamma-ray Glows (GRG)

- Second glow shows a Glow Burst (GGB) at time T3, seen using 0.1 second bin size.
- GGB is like a glow but much shorter, 0.4 second long here; and sitting at top of a GRG.
- r.f. dom: calculated levels where multiplication of seed electrons exceeds 5000, threshold where contribution from RFD is considered dominant
- altitude of end of avalanche is uncertain, hence several possible levels

CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

- On 29 July 2023 (20:30:20 to 20:31:40 UTC) the ER-2 aircraft at 20 km altitude recorded gamma-ray glows exceeding background by more than 8 times [Marisaldi et al., 2024].
- Previous ER-2 event (2017) showed only $\sim 40\%$ enhancements versus 100 to 730% here.
- Monte-Carlo simulations combining cosmic-ray secondary electrons, RREA atmospheric transport, and detector response were integrated with ALOFT-BGO, FECS, EFCM and CFLMA (ground) measurements.
- Relativistic feedback regime.** Seed electron multiplication factors repeatedly exceeded 5×10^3 (lasting sub-second to multiple seconds), placing both main glows—particularly the Glow Burst phase—in the relativistic feedback discharge regime. Likely applies to most, if not all, the ten Glow Bursts observed by ALOFT.
- Large discharge currents.** Current densities at $h = 13 \text{ km}$ were 4 to 26 times greater than the previous record (about $0.18 \mu\text{A}/\text{m}^2$ [Kelley et al., 2015]), suggesting possible total currents of tens of Amperes. These “RREA discharge currents” could significantly influence thunderstorm charging.
- Extended terminations.** Both glows ended more gradually than typical lightning-terminated (or reduced) events Kochkin et al. [2021]; here, conventional discharges are not happening at the glow decrease/termination, but can follow (always?).
- Broad impact.** ALOFT recorded hundreds of comparable glows (≥ 5000 counts s^{-1}) during ~ 30 flight-hours, suggesting RREA amplified by feedback may be a major competitor to conventional discharge, at least in summer storms near $\pm 30^\circ$ latitude.
- Open question.** Whether feedback-driven RREA also governs glows in other storm types (e.g., Japanese winter storms, Armenian mountain storms) remains unclear.

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Associated Paper in preparation for GRL

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